

COMPONENTS OF THE OBJECT OF PUBLIC MANAGEMENT OF TERRITORIAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the process of forming the components of the object of state management of territorial development of Ukraine. It is shown that in the conditions of deep socio-economic transformations, decentralization of power, European integration processes and military challenges, the issue of effective territorial development is gaining strategic importance for Ukraine. Territorial development today is not only a spatial organization of the economy, but a complex process that encompasses the economic, social, infrastructural, environmental and institutional dimensions of the functioning of regions and communities. Mechanisms of state management of territorial development are a key tool for ensuring balanced development of regions, reducing inter-territorial disparities, increasing the competitiveness of territories and the quality of life of the population. They must be adaptive to different types of territories, able to take into account their resource potential, demographic characteristics and level of economic activity. It has been established that the concepts and theories of sustainable territorial development form the necessary foundation for substantiating strategic priorities, mechanisms and instruments for achieving balanced and inclusive development of countries, regions and communities, taking into account economic, social and environmental imperatives. They are based on the key principles of sustainable development - integration of economic, social and environmental dimensions, orientation on the needs of current and future generations, ensuring justice and inclusiveness, taking into account the limitations of natural capital, adaptation to the local context. The implementation of these principles requires comprehensive and coordinated efforts of all levels of public administration and stakeholders with the active participation of the public. It has been proven that the economic, social and environmental components form the triune basis of sustainable territorial development. Achieving sustainability requires a comprehensive and integrated approach to these dimensions, taking into account their interrelationships, synergies and compromises for public administration entities. This involves the transformation of traditional models of socio-economic development and environmental management on the principles of efficiency, inclusiveness, balance and sustainability. The key drivers of such transformation are innovation, stakeholder cooperation, good governance, responsible production and consumption. The integration of social, economic and environmental dimensions of sustainable development is reflected in the goals and objectives of state management of territorial development in Ukraine.

Keywords: public management, state programs, integration, sustainable development, stakeholders, territorial development.

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Introduction

In the context of deep socio-economic transformations, decentralization of power, European integration processes and military challenges, the issue of effective territorial development is gaining strategic importance for Ukraine. Territorial development today is not only a spatial organization of the economy, but a complex process that encompasses the economic, social, infrastructural, environmental and institutional dimensions of the functioning of regions and communities. Mechanisms of state management of territorial development are a key tool for ensuring balanced development of regions, reducing inter-territorial disparities, increasing the competitiveness of territories and the quality of life of the population. They must be adaptive to different types of territories, able to take into account their resource potential, demographic characteristics and level of economic activity.

A significant contribution to solving this problem was made by: Baranovska T., Barau A., Bibri S., Biermann F., Bouckaert G., Dragan I., Elkington J., Ewing B., Grytsyshen D., Kanie N., Kim R., Krogstie J., Kryshtanovych M., Loretan R., Pike A., Rodriguez R., Sachs J., Sergiienko L., Tomaney J., Troupin S., Üрге-Vorsatz D.

The purpose of the article is a comprehensive analysis of the process of forming the components of the object of state management of territorial development of Ukraine.

Presentation of the main material

In the 21st century, the dominant paradigm of social progress is the Concept of Sustainable Development, which reflects public aspirations for social justice, economic growth and ecological balance. This concept was formed as a result of the awareness of global threats caused by population growth, climate change, limited natural resources, the spread of inequality and poverty [13].

The foundations of this concept were laid in the works of such economists as J.S. Mill, T. Malthus and others, who wrote about the problems of overpopulation, environmental degradation, and resource scarcity. However, the formulation of this concept took place in the second half of the twentieth century, as a reaction to the aggravation of global civilizational problems. Among the main stages in the formation of the Concept, it is necessary to highlight the work of the Club of Rome (1972), the UN conference in Stockholm (1972), the report of the Brundtland Commission (1987), the UN Conference in Rio de Janeiro (1992) and others.

The conceptual framework for sustainable development has been developed, in particular, in Agenda 21 (1992), the UN Millennium Declaration (2000), the Johannesburg Declaration on Sustainable Development (2002), the outcome document of the UN Conference on Sustainable Development (2012), and the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (2015) [18]. These documents formalized a global public consensus on the goals, principles and mechanisms for ensuring sustainable development at all levels of public governance.

The theoretical foundations of sustainable development include a number of basic concepts. The concept of the triple bottom line states that sustainable development should ensure the synergy of economic, social and environmental dimensions. The economic component involves the optimal use of limited resources and the introduction of resource-saving technologies. The social component is focused on maintaining the stability of social and cultural systems, fair distribution of benefits. The environmental component is aimed at ensuring the integrity of natural systems, their ability to self-recovery and adaptation [4]. This concept emphasizes the need for balance and integration of all three components, since progress in one of them without taking into account the others cannot be considered sustainable development.

The concept of needs and constraints emphasizes the need to satisfy the basic needs of all people and ensure equal opportunities to improve the quality of life in conditions of resource constraints. In this case, not only absolute limitations (the limits of resource renewal and waste assimilation) should be taken into account, but also relative limitations associated with

technology, social organization, cultural factors [17]. This concept draws attention to the problem of equitable distribution of resources both between current and future generations and within generations, given the deep inequalities in access to the benefits of development.

The concept of natural capital considers natural resources and ecosystem services as key assets that ensure human well-being. According to this concept, sustainable development requires the conservation and enhancement of natural capital, minimizing its depletion and degradation [7]. This includes renewable resources (biodiversity, soils, fresh water, etc.), non-renewable resources (minerals), as well as ecosystem services (climate regulation, water purification, plant pollination, etc.). This concept emphasizes the vital importance of natural systems that cannot be fully replaced by artificial capital.

The concept of the ecological footprint allows us to assess the anthropogenic impact on the biosphere through the ratio of humanity's needs for natural resources and the Earth's ability to restore them. Sustainable development assumes that humanity's ecological footprint should not exceed the planet's biopotential [5].

The concept of intergenerational and intragenerational justice emphasizes the ethical dimension of sustainable development. Intergenerational justice requires the preservation of opportunities for the development of future generations, while intragenerational justice requires the equitable distribution of the benefits and costs of development between different countries, regions, and social groups [8]. This concept emphasizes the need to overcome poverty, inequality, discrimination, ensure access of all people to basic goods and services, and participate in decision-making. It considers development not only as quantitative growth, but also as qualitative transformations that expand people's opportunities and contribute to their self-realization.

The practical implementation of the concept of sustainable development at the level of individual territories (countries, regions, communities) requires its adaptation to local conditions, needs and priorities. Sustainable territorial development provides for a model of functioning and evolution of territorial systems that ensures positive economic, social and environmental dynamics in the long term, taking into account the interests of current and future generations [10].

The concept of sustainable regional development focuses on endogenous factors of regional development, unlocking their internal potential, and stimulating interregional cooperation and cohesion [9; 11]. This concept is based on the fact that regions are not just passive recipients of national policies, but active subjects capable of mobilizing their own resources and competitive advantages to achieve sustainable development. It involves shifting the emphasis from a sectoral to a territorial approach, from exogenous to endogenous development factors, from short-term to long-term goals. The key drivers of sustainable regional development are considered to be human capital, innovation, infrastructure, effective institutions, social capital, and environmental responsibility. Multilevel governance plays a special role, ensuring coordination and synergy of efforts between regional and local authorities, business, and civil society.

The concept of sustainable rural development involves the diversification of the rural economy, increasing the income and quality of life of farmers, rational use of agricultural resources, and preservation of ecosystems and traditional landscapes [15]. This concept responds to the challenges faced by rural areas – depopulation, poverty, unemployment, degradation of natural resources, climate change, etc. It emphasizes the need to transition from a narrowly sectoral agrarian approach to multifunctional development of rural areas, which includes not only agriculture, but also non-agricultural activities – product processing, agritourism, folk crafts, renewable energy, environmental services, etc.

The place-based approach takes into account territorial specificity, endogenous potential, local assets and knowledge in the process of forming development policies, is an integrating

framework for implementing sustainable territorial development [12]. The approach is based on understanding the uniqueness of each territory, which is determined by a combination of natural, economic, social, and cultural factors. It assumes that development strategies and tools should be developed not according to universal templates, but taking into account the specifics of a particular place - its problems, needs, resources, and competitive advantages. Local knowledge and stakeholder participation play an important role in determining priorities and mechanisms for sustainable development. The place-based approach allows you to unlock the potential of territories that is underestimated by sectoral policies, and ensure the inclusiveness and legitimacy of the development process.

Various indicator systems covering economic, social, environmental and institutional parameters are used to assess and monitor progress towards sustainable territorial development. In particular, at the global level, the System of Global Indicators for the Achievement of Sustainable Development Goals has been developed [6]. This system allows countries to track their progress in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals and compare them with each other. At the EU level, a system of sustainable development indicators has been introduced in several thematic areas [1]. It is used to monitor the implementation of the EU Sustainable Development Strategy and assess the effectiveness of relevant policies. At the national and subnational levels, their own systems of sustainable development indicators are being developed, taking into account the specifics of countries and territories. In Ukraine, work is also underway to create a national system of indicators that should ensure monitoring of the achievement of sustainable development goals at the state, regional and local levels.

In general, theories and concepts of sustainable territorial development form a powerful foundation for substantiating strategic priorities, mechanisms and tools for achieving balanced and inclusive development of countries, regions and communities, taking into account economic, social and environmental imperatives. They are based on the key principles of sustainable development - integration of economic, social and environmental dimensions, orientation on the needs of current and future generations, ensuring justice and inclusiveness, taking into account the limitations of natural capital, adaptation to the local context. The implementation of these principles requires comprehensive and coordinated efforts of all levels of government and stakeholders with the active participation of the public.

The economic component of sustainable territorial development is aimed at ensuring sustainable and inclusive economic growth, which creates decent opportunities for employment and entrepreneurship, increases the productivity and competitiveness of the local economy, and ensures the efficient and rational use of resources [12].

The key aspects of the economic component of sustainable territorial development are as follows. First, diversification of the economic base of the territory. Sustainable development requires the formation of a diverse and sustainable economic structure that is based on several growth drivers and is less vulnerable to external shocks. This involves the development of both traditional and new sectors, taking into account local resources, knowledge and competencies, supporting small and medium-sized businesses, attracting domestic and foreign investment, stimulating innovation and entrepreneurship.

Secondly, increasing productivity and efficiency of resource use. Sustainable development of the territory requires continuous improvement of technologies, processes and production methods in order to increase labor productivity, minimize costs, reduce waste and pollution. This involves the implementation of resource and energy-efficient solutions, the development of a circular economy, the use of renewable energy sources, and the optimization of logistics and transport flows.

Third, the development of local value chains. Sustainable development of the territory involves maximizing local added value by deepening the processing of local raw materials,

developing local production clusters, establishing cooperative ties between enterprises, and stimulating the use of local goods and services. This allows for an increase in the multiplier effect of economic activity, creating new jobs and increasing the income of the local population.

Fourth, ensuring decent work and quality of employment. Sustainable development of the territory is inseparable from the creation of productive, safe and decently paid jobs for all segments of the population. This requires efforts to increase the level of employment, especially among youth, women and vulnerable groups, ensuring proper working conditions, respecting labor rights and standards, developing professional skills and competencies, promoting self-employment and micro-entrepreneurship.

Fifth, stimulating innovation and technological modernization. Sustainable development of the territory requires constant updating of the technological base, the introduction of innovations in various areas - from production to management. This involves the development of research and innovation infrastructure, commercialization of scientific developments, technology transfer, digitalization of the economy and public life, attracting investments in high-tech sectors, and development of creative industries.

The social component of sustainable territorial development is aimed at ensuring a high quality of life and well-being for all members of a territorial community, regardless of their socio-economic status, age, gender, ethnicity or other characteristics. It covers a wide range of issues related to meeting people's basic needs, ensuring equal access to public goods and services, developing human potential, strengthening social cohesion and inclusion [16].

The key aspects of the social component of sustainable territorial development are the following. First, overcoming poverty and reducing inequality. Sustainable development of the territory involves the eradication of extreme poverty, reducing the gap between the richest and poorest segments of the population, ensuring decent living conditions for all residents. This requires the implementation of effective social protection programs, redistribution of income, creating opportunities for productive employment and self-sufficiency.

Secondly, ensuring the accessibility and quality of basic services. Sustainable development of the territory involves universal access of the population to basic services, such as healthcare, education, social security, housing, transport, water supply and sanitation, energy supply, information and communication services, etc. In this case, it is important not only to expand the network of relevant institutions and infrastructure, but also to improve the quality and effectiveness of services in accordance with the needs and expectations of citizens.

Third, the development of human capital. Sustainable development of the territory requires continuous improvement of knowledge, skills and competencies of people as a key resource in the conditions of the knowledge economy. This involves modernizing the education and vocational training system, creating opportunities for lifelong learning, stimulating innovation and creativity, attracting and retaining talents. Particular attention should be paid to the development of entrepreneurial skills, digital literacy, critical thinking, social and emotional competencies.

Fourth, strengthening the health and well-being of the population. Sustainable development of the territory is inseparable from ensuring the physical, mental and social well-being of residents. This requires efforts to prevent and control diseases, promote a healthy lifestyle, create a safe and favorable living environment, develop recreational and sports facilities, provide quality medical care, and support vulnerable groups.

Fifth, ensuring social cohesion and inclusion. Sustainable development of the territory involves the formation of a cohesive community in which all members have a sense of belonging, trust and mutual support. This requires efforts to overcome social isolation and discrimination, integrate marginalized groups, develop social networks and civic activity, strengthen local identity and cultural heritage, prevent conflicts and violence.

The environmental component of sustainable territorial development is aimed at preserving and restoring natural ecosystems, biodiversity, environmental quality as a necessary condition for the health and well-being of current and future generations. It involves minimizing the negative impact of human activity on the environment, effective management of natural resources, increasing the resilience of territories to natural and anthropogenic threats [6].

The key aspects of the ecological component of sustainable territorial development are the following. First, the preservation and restoration of biodiversity. Sustainable development of the territory involves the protection and rational use of terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems, preventing the loss of flora and fauna species, restoring degraded natural areas. This requires the creation of protected areas and ecological networks, regulating economic activities in sensitive areas, combating poaching and illegal trade in species, and educational work on the value of biodiversity.

Secondly, sustainable management of natural resources. Sustainable development of the territory involves the balanced and effective use of renewable (water, soil, forests, etc.) and non-renewable (minerals) natural resources, taking into account the needs of current and future generations. This requires the implementation of the principles of integrated resource management, the use of resource-efficient technologies, waste minimization, combating illegal extraction of resources, and restoring disturbed landscapes.

Third, reducing environmental pollution. Sustainable development of the territory is inseparable from ensuring clean air, water and soil, minimizing emissions and discharges of pollutants, and safe waste management. This involves the implementation of environmental standards and regulations, encouraging "green" technologies and clean production, developing an environmental monitoring system, strengthening the environmental responsibility of business, and raising environmental awareness among the population.

Fourth, mitigating and adapting to climate change. Sustainable development of the territory requires efforts to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase resilience to the negative consequences of climate change. This involves the transition to a low-carbon economy, the development of renewable energy and energy efficiency, the preservation and increase of carbon sinks (forests, wetlands), and the adaptation of infrastructure and life support systems to climate risks.

Fifth, the development of environmental infrastructure and services. Sustainable development of the territory involves the formation of a developed infrastructure and service sector aimed at environmental protection and ensuring ecological safety. This includes water supply and drainage systems, treatment plants, waste management facilities, environmental monitoring networks, nature reserve fund facilities, eco-educational centers, etc. It is important to ensure equal access of the population to quality environmental services.

An integrated approach to social, economic and environmental components underlies the concept of sustainable territorial development. It involves finding a balance and synergy between these dimensions, taking into account their interrelationships and mutual influences when forming and implementing territorial development policies [1].

Sustainable territorial development also requires the establishment of effective mechanisms for horizontal and vertical coordination between different levels of government and stakeholders [2]. This involves overcoming departmental and administrative barriers, creating platforms for dialogue and cooperation, and agreeing on development goals and measures based on a shared vision for the future of the territory. Strategic planning for sustainable territorial development with the participation of a wide range of stakeholders plays an important role in this, which will be discussed in the next paragraph.

Another important aspect of ensuring balanced territorial development is the formation of a favorable institutional environment that stimulates and supports sustainability initiatives

at the local level [3]. This includes the development of an appropriate regulatory framework, financial and fiscal mechanisms, systems for monitoring and evaluating progress, institutions to support innovation and entrepreneurship, public participation mechanisms, etc. A special role is played by building the capacity of local authorities, businesses and civil society to integrate the principles of sustainable development into their activities.

Conclusions

Thus, the economic, social and environmental components form the triune basis of territorial development. Ensuring effective territorial development requires a comprehensive and integrated approach to these dimensions, taking into account their interrelationships, synergies and trade-offs for public administration entities. This involves the transformation of traditional models of socio-economic development and nature management on the principles of efficiency, inclusiveness, balance and sustainability. The key drivers of such transformation are innovation, stakeholder cooperation, good governance, responsible production and consumption. The integration of social, economic and environmental dimensions of sustainable development is reflected in the goals and objectives of public administration of territorial development in Ukraine.

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